

1 **The primary foreskin keratinocyte transcriptome following expression of the E7 oncoprotein.**

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7 We studied E7 function at the transcriptome level in primary human cells following retroviral gene
8 transduction. E7 activated expression of the cytokine receptor *Il1r2*. HPV E7 induced expression of claudin
9 genes *Cldn7* and *Cldn4*. HPV E7 expression was sufficient to activate cycling, with induction of *Cdk2*, *E2f2*
10 and *Pcna*. We describe here activation of *Sbp* and *Pitx1* by the E7 oncoprotein of human papillomavirus,
11 demonstrating active roles for E7 in transformation.

12 Citations

13 1. Hawley-Nelson, P., Vousden, K.H., Hubbert, N.L., Lowy, D.R. and Schiller, J.T., 1989. HPV16 E6
14 and E7 proteins cooperate to immortalize human foreskin keratinocytes. The EMBO journal, 8(12),
15 pp.3905-3910.

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